

Working with of High School Students' Parents: Innovative Approaches, Modern Methods

Qadamov Navrozbek Jasurbek ogli¹

¹ School No. 302, Yunusobot district, Tashkent city, Deputy director of spiritual and educational affairs

Abstract:

This article presents modern approaches and innovative methods of working with parents of high school students. In the article, the recommendations for the theme with using the "Digital parenting" method teaching the parents and their children to use the Internet and digital technologies correctly, developing psychological and emotional support skills with the "Parent - positive couch" method, improving effective communication skills with the "Parent: Communication" method.

Keywords: parent-school partnership, "Digital parenting" method, "Parent - positive couch" method, working with children, couch, "Parent: communication" method.

Adolescence is an important and difficult period of life for high school students, when they are not only finding their personal identity, but also determining their future professional directions. During this period, it is very important for parents to work with their children and help them. Here are some innovative approaches and modern methods that can be used in working with parents of high school students:

"Digital parenting" method (*digital parenting*) . Today, in an era of advanced technology, the concept of "Digital parenting" has appeared. This concept means that parents teach their children how to use the Internet and digital technologies properly. "Digital parenting" is becoming more complicated in the modern age, as technology is rapidly evolving. This approach helps parents to protect their children from internet safety while improving their skills to monitor their children's online activity and safety. Also, online training and platforms for parents are common these days. These platforms teach parents how to effectively communicate with their children, provide psychological support and emotional management. Online training allows parents to learn remotely.

Digital diaries and monitoring systems allow parents to constantly monitor their children's learning progress. These systems provide comprehensive information about students' grades, homework and truancy, and enable parents to actively communicate with their children.

It is necessary to create a special online portal and mobile applications to ensure effective cooperation between the school and parents using the "Digital parenting" method. These resources provide parents with regular information about their students' educational successes and challenges and enable them to be actively involved in the learning process.

Recommendations for the "Digital Parenting" method:

- parents should explain to their children the dangers of the Internet and inform them about measures to protect them.
- it is necessary to control the time children spend on the Internet and keep it in moderation.

"Parents are a positive couch" method (Positive parent coaching) . Parents play an important role in the education of their children. Their role is to control and establish order, but also to support the personal and emotional development of children. The "Parents - Positive Couch" method is aimed at this very goal and involves the formation of parents as coaches who provide positive support to their children.

The essence of the method is to help parents establish positive relationships with their children and provide them with support, guidance and motivation. The main goal of this method is to increase children's self- confidence, develop their abilities and help them achieve success.

The main principles of the method are constant positive communication with children, support and encouragement. Instead of reprimanding and criticizing, advice and guidance are more helpful. Children should always be supported and motivated to achieve their goals. It gives them confidence and determination. It is necessary to understand the needs and interests of children and act accordingly. It helps them feel valued. Children should be allowed to make independent decisions and take responsibility. It helps them develop life skills.

Advantages of the "Parent - positive couch" method. Through this method, trusting and positive relationships develop between parents and children. This, in turn, strengthens the family atmosphere. Children achieve personal development by being able to freely express themselves and make independent decisions.

With the support and motivation of their parents, children gain the strength and confidence they need to achieve their goals. Positive parenting is teaching parents skills to provide psychological and emotional support to their children. This approach helps parents in the following ways:

- teaching parents to understand and manage their own and their children's emotions;
- to help parents to develop their children's independent decision-making skills. Also, special psychological support centers can be established to solve psychological problems between parents and children . These centers provide training and counseling to parents on how to communicate effectively with their children and how to manage stress and emotional distress.

Practical recommendations:

- to the student (listen carefully to your children's thoughts and feelings. This helps them feel valued);
- provide positive feedback to the student (celebrate your children's successes and give them positive feedback. Scolding and criticism should be minimized);
- supporting learner interests (support your children's interests and help them find their direction);

- student problem-solving together (help your children increase their sense of responsibility by solving problems together. You need to be their coach and helper);

The "Parents - Positive Couch" method promotes a positive approach to raising children. Through this method, parents provide positive support and motivation to their children and make a great contribution to their personal and emotional development. Therefore, every parent should put this method into practice and serve as a mentor (positive coach) to their children.

"Parent: communication" method (Development of communication skills).

Effective communication between parents and children is an important component of family relationships. It not only strengthens family affection, but also plays an important role in raising children. From this point of view, the method "Parents: communication" deserves special attention.

The essence of the method is to develop open and effective communication between parents and children. The main goal of this method is to support the emotional and social development of children, to increase their self-esteem and self-confidence.

The main principles of the method are respect and equality. Parents should respect their children as individuals. Listening and respecting their opinions builds trust between parents and children.

Through active listening, children can better understand their thoughts and feelings. This, in turn, helps children feel valued . By showing an open interest in their children's lives and activities, parents can increase their motivation and establish deeper communication with them.

Supporting children, celebrating their successes, and acknowledging their mistakes will help build their confidence.

Advantages of the "Parent: communication" method. Through this method, healthy relationships between parents and children develop. They understand and respect each other better. Children's ability to freely express their feelings has a positive effect on their emotional development.

This method improves effective communication with parents and develops children's social skills. They learn the skills they need to find their place in society and be successful.

Practical recommendations. Parents should take time to communicate with their children every day. During this time, they should pay full attention to each other. You should ask them more questions. By asking questions about children's thoughts and feelings, you can better understand their inner world.

Allow them to express their feelings. Allowing children to freely express their feelings builds their self-confidence.

Set a positive example for them. Parents should be positive role models for their children. It is a good lesson for children when they demonstrate how they communicate.

"Parents: communication" method is important for strengthening family relations and raising children. Through this method, it is possible to develop open and sincere communication between parents and children, to strengthen their mutual trust, and to support the emotional and social development of children. Therefore, every parent should put this method into practice. For this, first of all, parents should learn to listen to their children. It helps to understand the important issues of adolescence.

In conclusion, it can be said that the above innovative approaches and modern methods of working with parents of high school students will help parents guide their children in the right direction and create a happy future for them. These techniques are effective tools for overcoming the complexities of adolescence and strengthening the bond between parents and children.

"Invitation to education" method . The "Call to education" method is one of the modern approaches to the educational process, the main goal of which is to increase the quality of students' knowledge in cooperation with family and school, to activate them and prepare them for life. This method is used when parents visit classes on "Open Doors".

Through this method, students are guided to actively participate in classes, help them express their thoughts freely, solve problems and acquire new knowledge. At the same time, preparing students for life, helping their personal and professional development is one of the important goals of the method.

Tasks of the "Invitation to Education" method:

Collaboration - student activation (in order to ensure the active participation of students in the course of the lesson, it is necessary to perform tasks through interactive methods and games with the participation of parents. This increases the interest of students in science, and increases their confidence);

Development of critical and creative thinking skills: To help students develop the ability to freely express their thoughts, reason and analyze problems.

Creative approach: giving students the opportunity to take a creative approach and develop new ideas, that is, develop skills to create unusual products in unusual conditions. Students learn to put their learning into practice through hands-on activities and a variety of interactive methods.

Therefore, by strengthening the cooperation between parents and the school, the ability of students to apply the knowledge acquired in the educational process in life is formed.

The essence of the "Call to Education" method. The "Call to Education" method is aimed at revitalizing the educational process and increasing its effectiveness. In cooperation with their parents, students learn knowledge more deeply and effectively using methods such as games, role-playing games, problem solving. Electronic resources and interactive programs are also widely used in this method. The close cooperation of the family and the school greatly contributes to the participation of students in the educational process and mastery of the subject.

The "Invitation to Education" method is one of the innovative approaches in the educational process, the main goal of which is to increase the quality of students' knowledge in cooperation with family and school, to activate them and prepare them for life.

In general, the "Invitation to Education" method serves to increase the quality of education by actively involving students in the educational process and developing their independent thinking, creative approach, and practical skills.

Active involvement of parents in the educational process of their children has a positive effect on the success of high school students. In order to meaningfully implement the "Invitation to Education" method, the following suggestions and recommendations should be taken into account:

introduction of special online platforms and applications to establish regular communication between school and parents;

send regular school news and student updates to parents via email or mobile apps;

gain the trust of parents by ensuring openness and transparency in the communication process;

receiving regular feedback from parents and taking their feedback into account. For this, parents should create favorable conditions for their children to learn effectively at home, and establish regular communication with the school administration and teachers and discuss the educational process of their children.

"Professional" method (Professional advice). High school students face great difficulties in determining their future career paths. The support of parents and teachers is important in this process. The "vocational" method, that is, the method of career counseling, is aimed at guiding students in choosing a future career and helping them to make a decision in this regard.

purpose of the "Professional-Vocational" method is to guide high school students in choosing a future career, to advise them in choosing a career, taking into account their interests, abilities and market requirements. Through this method, students identify their abilities, find ways to develop them, and prepare for successful future careers.

tasks of the "Profession" method are as follows:

- determination of professional direction (conducting tests and questionnaires to determine the interests and abilities of students);
- counseling (advising students about careers that match their interests and abilities);
- guidance in choosing a profession (showing students the right direction by providing information about market requirements and future professions);
- cooperation with parents (helping students choose a career in cooperation with parents and supporting their decisions);
- preparation for professional education (giving advice to students on how to prepare for entering professional educational institutions).

essence of the "Professional" method is an important tool to help students choose a future profession. Through this method, students identify their interests and abilities and learn how to develop them. By working in cooperation with parents and educators, students will have the opportunity to make more informed and correct decisions when choosing a profession. At the same time, this method helps students choose professions that match the market requirements.

"Profession-craft" method teaches students to make a conscious and reasonable decision when choosing a profession. Students identify their interests and abilities and take practical steps to develop them. Through close cooperation with parents and teachers, students are supported in choosing a career. By choosing professions that meet market requirements, students will become qualified personnel in the future and contribute to the development of society. Through the "Professional" method, students identify their interests and abilities and find ways to develop them.

The support of parents and teachers is important in this process. Especially high school students need the support of their parents in determining their future career paths. For this purpose, the family and the school should jointly conduct professional tests and organize meetings with career guidance staff in accordance with the children's abilities and interests. After all, choosing the right profession is the strength of the foundation of the future.

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